

**IS THERE ANY RELATIONSHIP BETWEEN
EMOTIONAL INTELLIGENCE AND CAREER
PERFORMANCE OF ACADEMIC STAFF OF PUBLIC
COLLEGES OF EDUCATION IN BENUE STATE,
NIGERIA? A FIELD REPORT**

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Abstract

The study investigated if emotional intelligence has any relationship with career performance of staff of public colleges of education in Benue State, Nigeria. The sample of this study was made up of 217 academic staff that were drawn from public colleges of education in Benue State, Nigeria. This study adopted the correlational research design. The instruments known as Academic Staff Emotional Intelligence Scale (ASEIS) and Academic Staff Career Performance Scale (ASCPS) were used to collect data for this study. ASEIS and ASCPS were trial tested which yielded the reliability values of 0.82 and 0.71 using Cronbach Alpha. Five research questions and five null hypotheses guided the study. The research questions were answered using multiple regression analysis while, the hypotheses were tested using ANOVA of regression analysis. The study revealed among other that there is no significant relationship between self-awareness and career performance [$F_{1, 217} = 7.821$; $p < 0.05$]. There is no significant relationship between self-management and career performance [$F_{1, 217} = 4.017$; $p < 0.05$]. There is significant relationship between self-awareness, self-management, social awareness, relationship management and career performance [$F_{1, 217} = 9.910$; $p < 0.05$]. It was recommended among that, since emotional intelligence predicts career performance of academics. Thus, emotional intelligence tests should be administered to individuals before they are recruited in the academic field.

Keywords: Emotional intelligence, career performance, and academic staff.

Introduction

The issue of career performance has become a source of concern to many countries in the world especially in countries described as under-developed nations where work is ever done but development remains a mirage. Inability of individuals to perform in various careers to some extent has manifested in some countries as political and social unrest, military insurgence, extreme poverty, hunger, outbreak and wide spread of diseases, and illiteracy. In Nigeria today, it is not surprising to discover that many workers cannot perform in their chosen careers. They have become clogs in the hub on which their organizations rotate. This emerging trend of vocational maladjustment has permeated every work of life in this country including our tertiary institutions. Although there are no clear statistical data on workers' career performance due to the dearth of scholarly research in this area, utterances by some eminent Nigerians confirm this. For instance, Ajiboye (2014) says many Nigerian workers do not have justifications for the salaries they collect. The author further said it is the maladjusted workers that want the 'pay' without doing the work. Poor attitude to work, lateness, absenteeism, theft, laziness, looting and vandalization which have led to liquidation of many public enterprises, low standard of service provision and low standard of education are all pointers to career maladjustment of workers.

The issue of poor attitude to work cut across various professions even the academics. Academics are lecturers in higher institutions such as universities, polytechnics and colleges of education. All are not left out in the ugly trends. It seems they too are not performing optimally in their chosen career. The main responsibility of the academics in a college of Education is to produce a teacher that is both intellectually and morally sound. Disappointingly, many products of Colleges of Education seem to perform grossly below expectation. Individuals, through interaction with

the press and scholarly publications, have pointed accusing fingers at the academics for their non-performance as it is causing the deterioration of educational standard. Adediwa (2012) and Adamu (2013) expressed worries over the many vices academics in tertiary institutions in Nigeria inflict on students. These include intentional failing of students for personal reasons and intentional omission of students' names in reporting of examination scores, sexual harassment of students, rape, assault, verbal abuse and refusal of students attending lectures. The researchers have observed some instances of non-performance among academics. In many academic union meetings, the academics were warned to refrain from issues of examination malpractice, absenteeism and molestation of students, but to no avail.

Adamu (2013); Lepine (2015); Ajayi, Achor and Otor (2019) observed that non-performance of academics in their careers could be caused by certain factors such as; poor remuneration, poor training, unavailability of work tools, welfare issues and personality. However, the researchers observed that, the career performance of the academics could also be affected by their emotional intelligence. Emotional intelligence is the prime attribute of personality that affects performance in work activities. Emotional intelligence is referred to as an individual's ability to understand, monitor and interpret his/her feelings or emotions (Barons, 2012). This basic understanding affects the way people relate peacefully and effectively on their jobs as well as in other spheres of life. The ability of people to live and relate harmoniously with one another irrespective of their emotional differences in a nut shell is known as emotional intelligence and has been identified as a key factor for career performance and success.

Career performance is defined as an individual's ability to accomplish tasks that are relevant to the goals of an organization that the individual works with, (Campbell, 2012). The author further explains that career performance is an individual level variable or something a single

person does. Mayer and Salovey (2013), define emotional intelligence as one's ability to perceive emotions and to access thoughts, to understand emotions and emotional knowledge, to effectively regulate emotions and to promote emotions and intellectual growth. In a more recent time, Emotional intelligence has been defined as one's ability to be aware of self emotions, detect emotions in others and manage emotional cues and information (Robins, Judge & Sanghi, 2009). It can be understood from those definitions that, people who know their own emotions are good at reading emotional cues. For instance, they know why they are angry or frustrated and how to express themselves without violating norms, on one hand, and on the other hand, being able to soothe other people's emotions, are emotionally intelligent and are most likely to be effective in their undertakings. Barons (2012) named the components of emotional intelligence as self awareness, self-regulation or management, social awareness and relationship management. According to Hall-stigart (2015), self-awareness is the process of understanding one's own character, feelings, motives and desires; it is an essential step in early self-development and a critical step in defining who one is. Emotional self-management is defined by Robbins, Judge and Sanghi (2009) as the ability to regulate one's emotions such that accepted standard behaviours or norms (rules, ethics or code of conduct) are not violated. Social awareness according to Goleman (2013) is the ability of being sensitive to other people's feelings. It involves empathy which means having astute awareness of others' emotions, concerns, and needs. It also includes ability of identifying people's unstated needs and the ability of reading situations objectively without biases and assumptions. Relationship management, also referred to as interpersonal skills, means the ability to inspire, influence and develops others (Goleman 2013). According to David (2015), interpersonal skills means, listening and taking criticisms non-defensively; it also means an

individual humbling him/herself to learn from his/her subjects or colleagues. Poor relationship management causes crises in an organization and brings about low productivity output. Ajayi (2017) opine that employees do not put their best performances at work places when they are unhappy with management, government or even their colleagues. Actions taken by aggrieved employees include strike actions, lock out and propaganda against the organization among others.

High emotional intelligence enable individuals know their worthiness, effectiveness and capability. It also gives individuals confidence and courage to perform on their jobs. High self-awareness is also considered to be important in a work place because of the role it plays in choosing a career. Individuals with high emotional intelligence skills according to Tramm and O'Hara (2014) demonstrate high measures of career satisfaction and performance. A possible explanation for this relationship is that employees with high emotional intelligence respond more effectively to work place stress and to emotional cues of co-workers. Akinboye (2011) opine that, to achieve success in work, life, business and social relationship, everyone needs emotional intelligences and competence. High emotional intelligence has been considered to be important in a work place. It has however been observed with dismay that, some academics in Colleges of Education exhibit some unaccepted behaviours which are associated with their level of emotional intelligence and invariably may tend to affect their career performance. However, it is scarcity of study to clearly show if emotional intelligence have any relationship with career performance. Low career performance is likely to be associated with low emotional intelligence which in turn affects learning outcome and the goals of the organization, thereby leading to career derailment. In response to this problem, this study investigated if emotional intelligence has any relationship with career performance of academic staff of public colleges of education in Benue State, Nigeria.

Research Questions

The following research questions guided this study:

1. What is the relationship between self-awareness and career performance of academic staff of public colleges of education in Benue State?
2. What is the relationship between self-management and career performance of academic staff of public colleges of education in Benue State?
3. What is the relationship between social awareness and career performance of academic staff of public colleges of education in Benue State?
4. What is the relationship between relationship management and career performance of academic staff of public colleges of education in Benue State?
5. What is the relationship between the combination of self-awareness, self-management, social awareness, relationship management and career performance of academic staff of public colleges of education in Benue State?

Hypotheses

The following null hypotheses were tested:

1. There is no significant relationship between self-awareness and career performance of academic staff of public colleges of education in Benue State
2. The relationship between self-management and career performance of academic staff of public colleges of education in Benue State is not statistically significant.
3. There is no significant relationship between social awareness and career performance of academic staff of public colleges of education in Benue State.
4. There is no significant relationship between relationship management and career performance of academic staff of public colleges of education in Benue State.
5. The relationship between the combination of self-awareness, self-management, social awareness, relationship management and career performance of academic staff of public colleges of education in Benue State is not statistically significant.

Research Design and Procedure

This study adopted the correlational research design. This type of study seeks to establish what relationship exists between two or more variables. Correlational design was considered suitable for this study because the researcher was seeking to establish a relationship between the independent variable (Emotional intelligence) and the dependent variables (Career performance). The study area was Benue State, Nigeria. The study was carried out in Colleges of Education in Benue State, Nigeria. The population of this study consists of 1003 academic staff in the two public Colleges of Education in Benue State, Nigeria namely College of Education Katsina-Ala and College of Education Oju. College of Education Katsina-Ala has a total number of 506 academic staff while College of Education Oju has 497 (Office of the registrar, COE K/Ala & COE Oju). A sample size of 217 respondents (110 from COE K/Ala & 107 from COE Oju) was selected from the population of 1003 using multi-stage sampling technique.

Two instruments known as Academic Staff Emotional Intelligence Scale (ASEIS) and Academic Staff Career Performance Scale (ASCPS) were used for data collection. The choice of questionnaires was considered because of the literacy level of the respondents. ASEIS was adapted using the Genos Emotional

Intelligence Inventory (GEII) developed by Gignac in 2008. The ASEIS items cut across four emotional intelligence variables namely; self-awareness, self-management, social awareness and relationship management. The instrument ASEIS contains 20 items which respondents are to respond to by indicating their level of agreement or disagreement on a 4 point scale. Academic Staff Career Performance Scale (ASCPS) was researchers constructed questionnaires based on what the researchers considered as useful and relevant information obtained from relevant literatures reviewed in the study. ASCPS consists of 20 items on academic career performance. The researcher adopted a four point scale. Questions on different activities of the academic staff were arranged to obtain information.

Both Academic Staff Emotional Intelligence Scale (ASEIS) and Academic Staff Career Performance Scale (ASCPS) items have four Likert-type options of Strongly Agreed (SA), Agreed (A), Disagreed (D) and Strongly Disagreed (SD). ASEIS and ASCPS is a 20-item questionnaire respectively bordering on the academics' emotional intelligence and career performance. The respondents were instructed to place a tick in the column with the response option that is appropriate to their opinion. For all items the scores are 4 for SA, 3 for A, 2 for D and 1 for SD for positive items and reversed for negative items. That is, SA-1, A- 2, D-3 and SD-4. Both ASEIS and ASCPS generated information on the level of emotional intelligence abilities and career performance respectively of the academic staff of Colleges of Education in Benue State, Nigeria.

Table 1: Regression Analysis of Self-Awareness and Career Performance

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate	Durbin-Watson
1	.789 ^a	.622	.559	.78019	2.067

The content validity of the instruments was carried out by three experts. Two experts in Psychology and one expert in Measurement and Evaluation, all from Benue State University Makurdi, Nigeria validated the instruments. To determine the reliability of the instruments, a trial test was conducted by the researcher. Thirty (30) respondents drawn from Gboko College of Education, Gboko were selected who were not part of the respondents used for the main study. Cronbach Alpha coefficients obtained showed that the instruments have satisfactory internal consistency to measure the variables of the study. Cronbach Alpha was used to estimate the reliability coefficients of the instruments which yielded a coefficient value of 0.82 and 0.71 respectively. Three research assistants were briefed to assist the researcher in administering copies of the questionnaires. The face to face method was used in the distribution of 217 copies of the questionnaire. To avoid missing copies of the questionnaire, the questionnaires were given to the respondents and collected by the research assistants the same day. The research questions were answered using multiple regression analysis while, the null hypotheses for the study were also tested using ANOVA of regression analysis to investigate the extent to which emotional intelligence account for career performance of academic staff of public colleges of education in Benue State, Nigeria.

RESULTS

Research Question One

What is the relationship between self-awareness and career performance of academic staff of Public Colleges of Education in Benue State? The answer to research question one is contained in Table 1

Table 1 shows the regression analysis of the relationship between self-awareness and career performance of academic staff of public colleges of education in Benue State, Nigeria. The result indicated that the correlation between self-awareness of academic staff and their career performance is 0.789 with a coefficient of determination of 0.622. This means that 62.2

percent variation of the career performance of academic staff can be attributed to their self-awareness.

Research question two

What is the relationship between self-management and career performance of academic staff of public colleges of education in Benue State? The answer to research question two is contained in Table 2.

Table 2: Regression Analysis of Self-Management and Career Performance

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate	Durbin-Watson
1	.643 ^a	.517	.439	.94408	2.697

Table 2 shows the regression analysis of the relationship between self-management and career performance of academic staff of public colleges of education in Benue State, Nigeria. The result indicated that the correlation between self-management of academic staff and their career performance is 0.643 with a coefficient of determination of 0.517. This means that 51.7 percent variation of the career performance of

academic staff can be attributed to their self-management.

Research question three

What is the relationship between social awareness and career performance of academic staff of public colleges of education in Benue State? The answer to research question three is contained in Table 3.

Table 3: Regression Analysis of Social Awareness and Career Performance

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate	Durbin-Watson
1	.701 ^a	.592	.410	.95037	1.992

Table 3 shows the regression analysis of the relationship between social awareness and career performance of academic staff of public colleges of education in Benue State, Nigeria. The result indicated that the correlation between social awareness of academic staff and their career performance is 0.701 with a coefficient of determination of 0.592. This means that 59.2 percent variation of the career

performance of academic staff can be attributed to their social awareness.

Research question four

What is the relationship between relationship management and career performance of academic staff of public colleges of education in Benue State? The answer to research question four is contained in Table 4.

Table 4: Regression Analysis of Relationship Management and Career Performance

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate	Durbin-Watson
1	.589 ^a	.483	.393	.52378	2.893

Table 4 shows the regression analysis of the relationship between relationship management and career performance of academic staff of public colleges of education in Benue State, Nigeria. The result indicated that the correlation between relationship management of academic staff and their career performance is 0.589 with a coefficient of determination of 0.483. This means that 48.3 percent variation of the career performance of

academic staff can be attributed to their relationship management.

Research question five

What is the relationship between the combination of self-awareness, self-management, social awareness, relationship management and career performance of academic staff of public colleges of education in Benue State? The answer to research question five is contained in Table 5.

Table 5: Regression Analysis of Self-Awareness, Self-Management, Social Awareness, Relationship Management and Career Performance

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate	Durbin-Watson
1	.797 ^a	.672	.294	1.92012	2.919

Table 5 shows the regression analysis of the relationship between the combination of self-awareness, self-management, social awareness, relationship management and career performance of academic staff of public colleges of education in Benue State, Nigeria. The result indicated that the correlation between the combination of self-awareness, self-management, social awareness, relationship management of academic staff and their career performance is 0.797 with a coefficient of determination of 0.672. This

means that 67.2 percent variation of the career performance of academic staff can be attributed to the combination of self-awareness, self-management, social awareness and relationship management.

Hypothesis one

There is no significant relationship between self-awareness and career performance of academic staff of public colleges of education in Benue State. The test to hypothesis one is presented in Table 6.

Table 6: Analysis of Variance of Self-Awareness and Career Performance

Model		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	26.948	1	26.948	7.821	.001 ^b
	Residual	104.213	216	5.001		
	Total	131.161	217			

ANOVA of regression analysis result in staff of public colleges of education in Benue State, Nigeria. Table 6 reveals that there is significant relationship

between self-awareness and career performance of academic staff of public colleges of education in Benue State, Nigeria.

Hypothesis two
The relationship between self-management and career performance of academic staff of public colleges of education in Benue State, Nigeria [$F_{1, 217} = 7.821$; $p < 0.05$]. The null hypothesis is therefore rejected. This implies that, there is significant relationship between self-awareness and career performance of academic staff of public colleges of education in Benue State is not statistically significant. The test to hypothesis two is presented in Table 7.

Table 7: Analysis of Variance of Self-Management and Career Performance

Model		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	11.703	1	11.703	4.017	.000 ^b
	Residual	1081.328	216	7.829		
	Total	1093.031	217			

ANOVA of regression analysis result in staff of public colleges of education in Benue State, Nigeria. Table 7 reveals that there is significant relationship

between self-management and career performance of academic staff of public colleges of education in Benue State, Nigeria.

Hypothesis three
There is no significant relationship between social awareness and career performance of academic staff of public colleges of education in Benue State, Nigeria [$F_{1, 217} = 4.017$; $p < 0.05$]. The null hypothesis is therefore rejected. This implies that, there is significant relationship between self-management and career performance of academic staff of public colleges of education in Benue State. The test to hypothesis three is presented in Table 8.

Table 8: Analysis of Variance of Social Awareness and Career Performance

Model		Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	14.163	1	14.163	1.173	.001 ^b
	Residual	2217.825	216	99.010		
	Total	2231.988	217			

ANOVA of regression analysis result in Table 8 reveals that there is significant relationship between social awareness and career performance of academic staff of public colleges of education in Benue State, Nigeria [$F_{1, 217} = 1.173$; $p < 0.05$]. The null hypothesis is therefore rejected. This implies that, there is significant relationship between social awareness and career performance of

academic staff of public colleges of education in Benue State, Nigeria.

Hypothesis four

There is no significant relationship between relationship management and career performance of academic staff of public colleges of education in Benue State. The test to hypothesis four is presented in Table 9.

Table 9: Analysis of Variance of Relationship Management and Career Performance

Model		Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	22.348	1	22.348	2.166	.001 ^b
	Residual	1005.303	216	58.743		
	Total	1027.651	217			

ANOVA of regression analysis result in Table 9 reveals that there is significant relationship between relationship management and career performance of academic staff of public colleges of education in Benue State, Nigeria [$F_{1, 217} = 2.166$; $p < 0.05$]. The null hypothesis is therefore rejected. This implies that, there is significant relationship between relationship management and career

performance of academic staff of public colleges of education in Benue State, Nigeria.

Hypothesis five

The relationship between the combination of self-awareness, self-management, social awareness, relationship management and career performance of academic staff of public colleges of education in Benue State is not statistically significant. The test to hypothesis five is presented in Table 10.

Table 10: Analysis of Variance of the Combination of Self-Awareness, Self-Management, Social Management, Relationship Management and Career Performance

Model		Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	1828.036	4	457.009	9.910	.000 ^b
	Residual	687.908	213	94.031		
	Total	2515.944	217			

ANOVA of regression analysis result in Table 10 reveals that there is significant relationship between the combination of self-awareness, self-management, social awareness, relationship management and career performance of academic staff of public colleges of education in

Benue State, Nigeria [$F_{4, 217} = 9.910$; $p < 0.05$]. The null hypothesis is therefore rejected. This implies that, there is significant relationship between relationship management and career performance of academic staff of public colleges of education in Benue State, Nigeria

Discussion of findings

The study investigated if emotional intelligence variable such as self-awareness, self-management, social awareness and relationship management have any relationship with career performance of academic staff of public colleges of education in Benue State, Nigeria. The findings revealed that there is significant relationship between self-awareness and career performance of academic staff of public colleges of education in Benue State, Nigeria. The finding agrees with Goleman (2013) who revealed that, individuals who have high self-awareness know about their strengths and weakness, their abilities and limitations and so are able to select tasks that are commensurable with their abilities, or tasks that they can excel in. It is also understood that self-awareness enables individuals to learn from their mistakes, know where they need to improve and when to work with others who have complementary strengths (Cherniss, 2010). These imply that for anybody to perform well in his career, the person must have a certain level of self-awareness to enable him/her choose the career that is appropriate with his/her abilities. The researcher however observed that some academic staff lack self-awareness and perhaps choose their career without knowing the implications. This might be one of reasons for their low career performance. Since it is found out in this work that self-awareness has strong positive relationship with career performance of academics precautions have to be taken when employing and staff who are already on the job should be identified and made to receive counseling in that direction.

Another major finding of this study is that there is significant relationship between self-management and career performance of academic staff of public colleges of education in Benue State, Nigeria. Emotional self-management is characterized by the ability to regulate distressing affects like anxiety, anger and the inhibition of emotional impulsivity. The finding agrees with that

of Robbins, Judge and Sanghi (2009) who said emotional self-management manifests as self control, absence of distress and disruptive feelings, being unfazed in difficult situation and dealing with a hostile person. Emotional self-management involves having initiative which has been proven by Humphery (2011) to have significant contribution to social interaction. The academic staff in colleges of education in the state is responsible for training teachers who are to work in the primary and secondary schools. High level of emotional self-management can enable them to display self-discipline as the students will benefit and also emulate.

This study also found out that there is a significant relationship between social awareness and career performance of academic staff in the study. Social awareness manifests in three emotional competencies which are empathy, service and organizational awareness. The finding shows that social awareness is statistically significant to influence career performance. This finding agrees with that of Barons (2012) who reported that, physicians high in social awareness have the ability to read the current of emotions and realities and perform better in their career than their average colleagues. It was also found out by Barons (2012) that people who have high social awareness find it easy to establish rapport with people, both in the place of work and outside work places. Academic staff needs to create and maintain good rapport with students and colleagues, for it enhances performance in the academic arena. Social awareness serves as a facilitating factor to career performance of academic world over therefore, stake holders in the educational system in the state should not ignore or overlook it.

Another finding of this study is that there is a significant relationship between relationship management and career performance of academic staff in the study. Relationship management is characterized by persuasiveness, effective

communication, conflict management, visionary leadership, building bonds and collaboration, and team work. This finding corresponds with the findings of David (2015) who reported that individuals that have relationship management skills sense others' reactions and fine-tune their own responses to move interaction in the best direction. The finding also agrees with that of Hallstigart (2015) found out that relation management enhances effective communication which is key to effective performance in the academic career. Conflict management and effective communication are skills that have positive effect on career performance in a workplace like a college of education where large number of people with diverse backgrounds like religious, tribal, social and economic backgrounds converged. Where people come together in such a large number conflicts are inevitable. And when conflicts are allowed to escalate they hinder effective performance and consequently the goals of the organisation are not achieved. It is in the light of this notion that Cherniss (2010) proposed that leaders should be imparted with relationship management skills so that they can articulate and arouse enthusiasm for clearest vision and mission.

Another important finding of the study is that self-awareness, self-management, social awareness and relationship management significantly predict career performance of the academic in the study. This finding agrees with the finding of Goleman (2013) who reported that emotional intelligence tends to predict career performance more than cognitive intelligence. Their finding also showed that emotional intelligence is necessary in effective career performance especially in careers that require a high degree of emotional labour, for example lecturing, selling, banking, police and health work. The finding in this study generally seem to agree with those of different researchers in Africa and other continents of the world. This is probably because, emotional intelligence is a universal phenomenon and its

applicability cut across all cultures. In any environment an individual is operating, one's abilities to identify, understand, monitor and interpret one's own emotions and that of other people one relates with seems to be viewed in the same perspective and tends to affect performance in any establishment or environment.

Conclusion

It is evident from the findings of this study that emotional intelligence variable such as self awareness, self management, social awareness and relationship management are determinant of career performance of academic staff of public colleges of education in Benue State, Nigeria. This means that there will be an improvement in an academic's career performance if there is an increase in acquisition of emotional intelligence skills and the reverse will be the case if there is a decrease in emotional intelligence skills.

Recommendations

Based on the findings, the following recommendations were made:

1. Since emotional intelligence predicts career performance of academics. Emotional Intelligence tests should be administered to individuals before they are recruited in the academic field.
2. In order to encourage harmonious relationship between academic staff and the students should be provided the opportunity to report their opinion about the performances of their lecturers as a way of unveiling the lecturers' competence on emotional intelligence skills.
3. Courses on components of emotional intelligence should be integrated in the teacher training curriculum. Every teacher training institution should have a functional counseling unit to assist maladjusted workers on emotional intelligence skills.

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